

Beacons

Beacons are.

Cat in an environment with objects

Beacons are vision-labeled objects in a simulation,

Though all of them is able to be considered as a Publisher of Signal (a beacon)

Most likely these will undergo a filtering process;

Some of the more predictable ones (actually just terrain)

Are scrubbed; (for optimization); meanwhile

The most dynamic ones are usually then labeled as SocialTypes

To then have their own decisionNodes for countering every Signal

That they produce (the cat will then hedge/ add weight / influence decision)

There are also significant mention for SelfSocial nodes

(a placeholder for tracking self-identity awareness)

GIST:

Cat vs environment with objects

Every object; or even things with a noticed Pattern

Is considered a Beacon;

We can decide on whether to run a wholesale scan; to then

Decide the Predictability % and the nearest ObjectType

Of Each entity; then treat them as if

They would continuously emit a signal

That the Current Agent Cat need to respect

(by adding weights ;or triggering hedges to simulations)

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Make beacons table

Run a process to check nearest, run confirmation

at modTude

then, after checking, publish pulses

for weights onto SIM

i.e. a Social Cortex processing the

HUMAN -> HUMAN OWNER.

a system where we take a active affector depending on

What the labeled HUMAN would do

(and their effectors too; by mood for example)

From the sim / thoughts involving what their mood do to their action

(can be simplified; often simplified; by math / FE range)

Onto our cat's action space

Formal Process:

1. Scan everything in vision for PATTERNS
2. Label all patterns and divide them by Significance
3. Significance = currently wholly decided by
4. [LEARNED]EpigeneticObjectTableX (a progression of [BASE]EpigeneticTable)

After we label all patterns

5. Label each object if they are distinct by Pattern:
(specific pattern that the Cat wakes up today; and decide
in its immediate (medium term memory) of terrain-associated awareness;
Or identity-associated awareness (any kind of stashed Identity-related-Memory)
6. Objects distinct by pattern are labeled OTSP-Named-1-% (object-type-scanned-pattern)
7. Objects distinct by type [but static] are labeled OTSA-Named-1-%

(object-type-scanned-A(static object)-Name-1)

1 = is then changed to label number

% = is then changed to inverted similarity %

Author note: “naming conventions are subject to FREQUENT CHANGES / revamp based on associated framework , that will be attached as a naming convention update / description”

(please help)

8. Objects distinct by type [but dynamic] are labeled OTSB-Named-1-%

(object-type-scanned-B(dynamic object)-Name-1)

1 = is then changed to label number

% = is then changed to inverted similarity %

9. Objects distinct by type [but Social] are labeled OTSSB-Named-1-%

(object-type-scanned-S(social)-B(other social)-Name-1)

With same other assignment; social objects are always assigned Sim Node

Social objects are distincted by a special table to elevate normal objects
(take the existing table ; and uplabel them to social)

10. Just for clarity in our important mechanism in the paper; there is a
OTSSA-Named-1-%

Which is a [self-social] label
(object-type-scanned-S(social)-A(self social)-Name-1)

This way; Identities (any psychological equivalent) are able to be represented
As if they are whispering selves that adds weight or simulatable despite not being very clearly depicted
Consider them >:D ghosts

11. This is especially useful when a EpigeneticChain/ CYC

Calls upon certain simulations (known; very frequent actually)
On which outcome matrix; highly depends on a back-and-forth Stancing with the current agent.
Therefore; the selves could be a stash of "recent label" attached to a Self equivalent;
To then both be applied a same usual rule; on how a Social + Social would behave / call a Sim
(so they can easily port a simulation that usually decides
a normative outcome -> thus weight -> between two Social creature;
to just swap one with a Self equivalent with a distinct label)

12. To note on the underlying framework that relies on Quickcalc mechanism (every
simulation grades are subject to simplification to mathematical formula; depending on their
Free Energy % threshold for novelty); this links the Social Cortex Sims to quickcalc)

Formal Description:

In a simulation; All entities (in the mind of the “Current Agent”) is considered a Publisher.

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(ideally this would be so; even Walls are publisher; or a wall that is identified having

A certain pattern that the initial; low grade scanner of the agent; notices)

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They publish Signals. Signals are usually weights or Hedges;

or specific processing node for Hedges.

Back to the fact that all entities are considered Publishers, but.

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But for optimization reasons; these are then classified onto a certainty spectrum.

Some of them are almost absolutely predictable , such as Walls, Rocks. etc

(unless labeled with a certain *recognition layer* (for patterns / etc))

Some of them are less predictable; unfamiliar pattern or noticed discrepancy

Some of them are dynamic; thus usually always come with a noticeable HEDGING signal

Some of them are Highly Dynamic (social entities); they come with a prediction matrix and their own linkage to a node that process how their back-and-forth behavior,

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(that prediction matrix node is pretty much linked to the equivalent of Empathy)

(a depictable / composable simulated reactions / predictions of such entity in a separate space;)

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Moving back to the term of BEACONS and the

signals that they publish:

In our framework; as with the processing of signals;

(producing hedges / weights)

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These BEACONS

Will then produce their specific labeled; Hedges

(depending on the nearest object template that they represent)

And they have their own TREE dynamic on which nodes of processing should happen

(this is directly encoded in a [temporary/updated]Epigenetic table that

Starts from a Baseline (Inherited) reactionary table of actions

Onto a Learned (modified) reactionary table of actions (reactions in this case).

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Discussion

Human. Cat. Sees environment v

Scans v

Patterns -> types v

Threshold of Uncertainty v

ObjectTypes

ObjectTypes are sometimes elevated onto SocialTypes

Everyone of those are BEACONS with signal pulses

(in biology; this is likely a chemical that even as it undergoes degradation (pulse ends) ; simply linger awhile;)

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SocialCortex is always active

Attaching Beacon to everything identifiable

(its an organ with a Processing Node that *has to be filled*)

(an absence of patterns simply mean the Organ (biological) will eat Anything / any
brainchem signal and make it a social)

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(this reality actually implies that objects are initially labeled as Social)

instead of the other way around

as in; in a biological being;

everything is first considered to be of the highest grade

before they are downgraded

but since we are trying to make a smushed-up

quickly cooked version of a working agent with

presumption of optimizing need

we start this way instead!

(just make a empty port to fill with patterns then upgrade)

(in reality; this is a two-fold process where the Vision Cortex labels the pattern; talks to
Social cortex; then talks back to the labeling central (not sure which brain part that is))

(we decide to combine Vision + Social; onto a working agent)

(thus simply decide from bottom up)

Summary

We hope to construct an agent by attaching a (any) Vision Model

With the appropriate labeling regime (labeling regime is subject to change and revamp!)

With the appropriate channel for processing the (labeled types)

Processing comes in form of BEACONS; with signal pulse

REFERENCES

Prior discussion / Youtube topic:

() lightcone# () globalworkspacetheory

() activeinferenceenvironmentagents (active types / the name for the types)

() epigeneticbases# () morphic(episimilar) () epigenes

() blindness/absence of signal

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